

Do Financial Reports Matter to Investors? Evidence on Relevance and Decision-Usefulness in Sri Lanka

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the extent to which information disclosed in corporate financial reports supports investor decision-making in Sri Lanka. Drawing on decision-usefulness and information asymmetry perspectives, the research develops and empirically validates a construct to capture the relevance of financial reporting from investors' perspectives. Using a quantitative, user-focused approach, primary data were obtained from active investors with accounting knowledge and analysed through Exploratory Factor Analysis, Confirmatory Factor Analysis, and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling. The results reveal that relevance is represented by six distinct information categories: forward-looking disclosures, cash flow information, segmental reporting, risk-related disclosures, fair value measurement information, and capital structure details, operationalised through twenty-eight validated indicators. Reliability and validity assessments confirm the soundness of the proposed measurement model. Further analysis demonstrates that the relevance of financial information exerts a strong and statistically significant influence on the decision-usefulness of annual reports, accounting for a substantial proportion of variation in investors' decisions. The findings provide empirical evidence that financial reports remain an important input for investment decisions in Sri Lanka and highlight the importance of enhancing relevant disclosures to improve the practical value of financial reporting in emerging capital markets.

KEYWORDS: Financial Reporting, Relevance of Financial Information, Decision-usefulness, Information Asymmetry

I. INTRODUCTION

Financial reporting represents the principal channel through which organisations convey information about their financial performance, financial position, and governance practices to external stakeholders. Through a system of recognised accounting standards and reporting conventions, financial reports enable users to evaluate how economic resources are obtained, deployed, and managed over time. Prior research highlights that well-prepared financial reports play a critical role in reducing information asymmetry between corporate insiders and market participants, thereby supporting efficient capital allocation and informed decision-making (Healy & Palepu, 2001; Bushman & Smith, 2001). Beyond numerical disclosures, contemporary financial reporting incorporates narrative explanations, risk-related disclosures, and forward-looking commentary, which collectively enhance users' understanding of corporate activities and prospects.

Within this study, relevance is conceptually understood as the extent to which financial information has the potential to influence investors' economic decisions by offering insights that are timely, meaningful, and closely aligned with their information needs. Relevant information assists investors in evaluating historical performance, interpreting current financial conditions, and forming expectations regarding future cash flows and risks. This perspective is consistent with the view that the usefulness of financial reporting depends not merely on the volume of information disclosed, but on its ability to support judgements that matter in investment contexts (IASB, 2018; Barth et al., 2001).

Importantly, relevance is not treated as an inherent property of financial information in isolation. Rather, it is shaped by the decision environment in which information is applied. Financial disclosures become relevant when they

correspond to the informational requirements of users and contribute to reducing uncertainty associated with investment choices. In this sense, relevance is closely linked to the predictive and confirmatory roles of accounting information, enabling investors to assess both future prospects and prior expectations (Francis et al., 2004; Kothari, 2001).

From a financial reporting perspective, relevance is widely recognised as a qualitative characteristic that enhances the decision-usefulness of reported information. Disclosures that are appropriately selected, sufficiently detailed, and clearly connected to economic decision-making are more likely to influence investor behaviour. Conversely, information that is technically accurate but lacks decision-related significance offers limited practical value to users. Accordingly, relevance is central to understanding how financial reports function as decision-support tools rather than as mere historical records. Accordingly, this study is focused on two research objectives;

01. *Develop a measurement model to measure the “Relevance” of financial statements based on the literature, which facilitates the decision-making scenarios of Investors.*
02. *Explores the contribution of the developed measurement model of the variable “Relevance” toward providing decision-useful information for investors in the Sri Lankan context.*

Overall, relevance constitutes a fundamental dimension of financial reporting quality, reflecting the degree to which reported information contributes to informed investment decisions within a given institutional and economic context. By examining relevance in relation to decision usefulness, this study seeks to provide insights into how financial reporting can better serve the needs of investors and enhance the effectiveness of capital market decision-making.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The question of whether financial reports continue to matter to investors has been a long-standing concern in accounting and capital market research. Prior literature has consistently examined the extent to which financial reporting information supports investor decision-making by reducing information asymmetry and improving market efficiency (Healy & Palepu, 2001; Scott, 2015). Early empirical studies emphasised the usefulness of financial statements in explaining share prices and returns, thereby reinforcing the relevance of accounting numbers for investment decisions (Ball & Brown, 1968; Beaver, 1968).

However, more recent research raises concerns about the continuing decision-usefulness of traditional financial disclosures, citing issues such as excessive disclosure volume, managerial discretion, and the growing availability of alternative information sources (Lev & Gu, 2016; Barker & Penman, 2020). Within this evolving debate, analysing the relevance and decision-usefulness of financial reports from

investors’ perspectives provides important insights into how accounting information is actually interpreted and utilised in practice. This issue is particularly salient in emerging capital markets such as Sri Lanka, where differences in regulatory frameworks, disclosure quality, and investor sophistication may influence the way financial reports contribute to investment decisions (Alfaraih & Alanezi, 2011; Hassan, 2018). The present study is based mainly on two theories as explained below.

A. *Decision-Usefulness Theory*

This study is primarily anchored in decision-usefulness theory, which represents the cornerstone of contemporary financial reporting research. Decision-usefulness theory posits that the fundamental objective of financial reporting is to provide information that assists users, particularly investors in making rational economic decisions. From this perspective, financial reports are considered valuable only insofar as they enhance users’ ability to evaluate financial performance, assess financial position, and form expectations about future outcomes (Beaver, 1998; Staubus, 2000). The Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting issued by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) reinforces this view by emphasising relevance as a key qualitative characteristic that enables financial information to influence users’ decisions (IASB, 2018). In the context of this study, decision-usefulness theory provides the primary lens through which the relevance of financial information disclosed in annual reports is evaluated from the investors’ perspective.

B. *Information Asymmetry Theory*

Closely related to decision-usefulness theory is information asymmetry theory, which explains the existence of unequal access to information between corporate insiders and external stakeholders. Investors typically possess less firm-specific information than management, creating uncertainty and potential inefficiencies in capital markets. Financial reporting is therefore viewed as an essential mechanism for mitigating information asymmetry by disclosing relevant and credible information to market participants (Akerlof, 1970; Healy & Palepu, 2001). Prior literature suggests that higher-quality and more relevant financial disclosures reduce uncertainty and improve investors’ decision-making processes (Lambert, Leuz, & Verrecchia, 2007). This theory is particularly relevant in emerging markets such as Sri Lanka, where alternative information channels may be less developed and investors rely more heavily on formal financial reports.

C. *Relevance of Financial Information*

Financial information is considered relevant if it has the potential to influence the decisions made by users of accounting information. The relevant information has predictive value (i.e. the ability to use the financial information to protect future outcomes), confirmatory value (i.e. the ability to provide feedback on previous evaluations

and facilitate users to confirm or correct previous decisions), or both (IASB, 2018). Relevant information is more useful to the users when making sustainable economic decisions (Dima, 2013). Further, relevant information should be able to provide insight into business opportunities, risks, as well as possible future scenarios for the company (Jonas and Blanchet, 2000). If the omission or falsification of financial data has an impact on economic decisions made by the users, it is considered relevant information (Kieso et al., 2019). Accordingly, the first research hypothesis of the research is developed as follows;

H1: Selected main information dimensions and sub-information items significantly contribute to measuring the ‘Relevance’ of Financial reports.

As key information dimensions and their respective sub-information items related to the measurement of variable ‘Relevance’ as presented in Table 01 were employed.

Table 01: Main Information Dimension and Sub-information item used to measure the ‘Relevance’.

Main Information Dimension	Sub-information items		Literature
	Code	Item Name	
Forward-looking Information (RFL)	RFL01	Projected Revenue Growth	Bandara, 2020; Celik et al., 2006
	RFL02	Projected Profit Growth	Bandara, 2020; Celik et al., 2006
	RFL03	Projected Earnings per Share (EPS) Growth	Alattar & Al-Khater, 2008; Bandara, 2020
	RFL04	Projected increase in Market Price per Share (MPS)	Bandara, 2020; Joshi & Mirshekary & Saudagaran, 2005; XRB, 2016
	RFL05	Potential Business Prospects	Bandara, 2020
	RFL06	Upcoming strategies will be implemented to attain either revenue or earnings objectives.	Bandara, 2020; Mirshekary & Saudagaran, 2005
	RFL07	Factors impacting the achievement of revenue or	Bandara, 202; De Zoyza & Bhati, 2011

		earnings targets.	
	RFL08	Expected increase in dividend per share.	Bandara, 2020; Celik et al., 2006; De Zoyza & Bhati, 2011; Naser et al.; 2003
	RFL09	Details regarding upcoming non-financial key performance indicators.	Bandara, 2020; CASL 2017
	RFL10	Other factors (Company plans, Projects, Capital Expenditure Plans, etc.)	Celik et al., 2006
Cash Flow Information (RCF)	RCF01	Projected cash flows	Bandara, 2020
	RCF02	Historical cash, bank and other cash equivalent details.	Bandara, 2020
	RCF03	Cash flow comparison data spanning multiple previous years.	Bandara, 2020
	RCF04	Reasons or justifications for changes in previous cash flows (operating, investing, or financing activities).	Bandara, 2020
	RCF05	Details of cash flows segmented by product, sector, or geographical classification.	Bandara, 2020
	RCF06	Other factors (Additional information, cash, bank and other cash equivalent details, etc...)	Mirshekary & Saudagaran, 2005

Segmental Information (RSI)	RSI01	Segmented information regarding revenue.	Bandara, 2020; IASB, 2013; Mirshekary & Saudagaran, 2005,
	RSI02	Comparative information on revenue by segment.	Bandara, 2020; IASB, 2013; CASL 2017
	RSI03	Segment-specific information on historical profit.	Bandara, 2020; IASB, 2013; CASL 2017
	RSI04	Projected profit by segment.	Aleksanyan & Danbolt, 2015; Bandara, 2020; XRB, 2016
	RSI05	Segment-specific non-financial key performance indicators.	Bandara, 2020; PwC, 2017.
	RSI06	Other factors (providing non-mandatory information)	Aleksanyan & Danbolt, 2015
Information on Measuring Assets, Liabilities, and Equity at Fair Value (RFV)	RFV01	Assets, liabilities, and equity line items are valued at their original cost.	Bandara, 2020
	RFV02	Assets, Liabilities and Equity line items are measured at fair value.	Bandara, 2020; Beest et al., 2009; Braam & Beest, 2013, CASL 2017,
	RFV03	Explaining the valuation techniques utilized for assets, liabilities, and equity components.	Bandara, 2020; Hooks et al., 2002; IASB, 2011;
	RFV04	Details regarding changes in the fair value.	Bandara, 2020
	RFV05	Other Factors (Other non-financial information on	Braam & Beest, 2013

Capital Structure Information (RCS)	RCS01	valuations) Explanations of the Gearing Ratio (Debt-to-Equity) employed to finance assets.	Bandara, 2020; Cascino et al., 2014; XRB, 2016
	RCS02	Comparative information on changes in the capital structure.	Bandara, 2020; Benjamin & Stanga, 1977; PAAinE, 2009
	RCS03	Details regarding the composition of non-current liabilities.	Bandara 2020
	RCS04	Other Factors (Other related information such as dividend payment, finance cost, etc.)	Cascino et al., 2014
Risk-Related Information (RRR)	RRR01	Details on the company's risk profiles for the current year.	Amran et al., 2008; Bandara, 2020
	RRR02	Information regarding risk mitigation strategies.	Bandara, 2020; Botosan, 2004; KPMG 2014
	RRR03	Comparative analysis of risk profiles against previous years.	Bandara, 2020; Botosan, 2004; KPMG 2014, XRB, 2016
	RRR04	Other factors (information relating to predicting financial distress and credit ratings)	Cascino et al., 2014

D. Decision-Usefulness

The concept of decision-usefulness occupies a central position in financial reporting research, as the primary purpose of financial disclosures is to support investors in making informed economic choices. Financial information is regarded as decision-useful when it assists users in evaluating alternative courses of action, assessing financial performance and position, and forming expectations about future outcomes. Among the qualitative attributes of financial

reporting, relevance plays a particularly important role in this process. Information is considered relevant when it has the capacity to influence investor judgements by reducing uncertainty and enhancing understanding of matters that are material to investment decisions. In this sense, relevance is closely linked to the ability of financial reports to provide timely, meaningful, and contextually appropriate information rather than merely presenting historical figures. When annual reports contain information that aligns with investors’ informational needs, such disclosures are more likely to be incorporated into decision-making processes, thereby strengthening the overall decision-usefulness of financial reporting.

To measure the “Decision-usefulness”, information dimensions and their respective sub-information items related in Table 02 were employed;

Table 02: Main Information Dimension and Sub-information item used to measure the ‘Decision-Usefulness’.

Information Dimensions		Literature
Code	Item Name	
DU01	Usefulness of information	IASB, 2018 Scott, 2015 Healy, 2001 Dechow, 2010
DU02	Adequacy of information	Alfaraih, & Alanezi, 2011. Botosan, 1997, Hassan, 2018. Naser & Nuseibeh, 2003.
DU03a	Usefulness of Statement of Financial Position	Barth et al, (2001) Penman (2013) Easton, (1999)
DU03b	Usefulness of Income Statement	Ball & Brown, (1968) Dechow, (1994) Kothari, (2001)
DU03c	Usefulness of Cash Flow Statements	Dechow et al, (1998). Bowen et al, (1986). Farshadfar & Monem (2013).
DU03d	Usefulness of Statement of Changes in Equity	IASB (2018). Beest, et al, (2009). Lee & Tweedie (1981).
DU03e	Usefulness of Notes to Financial Statements	Bradbury (1992). Barth et al. (2012). PwC (2017).
DU03f	Usefulness of Accounting Policies	Fields et al. (2001). Beattie et al. (2004). Nobes & Stadler (2015).
DU03g	Usefulness of	Chambers et al.

	Statement of Other Comprehensive Income	(2007). Kanagaretnam et al. (2009). Barker (2010).
DU03h	Usefulness of Auditor's Report	Hodge, et al. (2009). Gay & Schelluch (1993). IAASB (2015)
DU03i	Usefulness of the Director's Report	IASB (2010). Li (2010). Merkl-Davies & Brennan (2011).
DU03j	Management Discussion and Analysis	Healy & Palepu (2001) Li (2010) Brown & Tucker (2011)
DU03k	Usefulness of Corporate Governance Information	Bushman, & Smith (2001). Brown & Caylor (2006). Solomon (2013).
DU03l	Usefulness of CSR Information	Dhaliwal et al. (2011). Clarkson et al. (2013). Freeman (1984).
DU03m	Usefulness of Segmental Information	Hope et al. (2009). Berger & Hann (2003).
DU03n	Usefulness of Statistical Summary	Lee & Tweedie (1981). Courtis (2005). Beattie (2014).
DU03o	Usefulness of the Sustainability Report	Eccles et al. (2014). Friede et al. (2015).
DU04	Restriction on to use of annual reports	Lev & Gu (2016). Elliott et al. (2015). Williams & Ravenscroft (2015).

IASB (2018), by presenting its improved version of the Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting, mentioned that the provision of decision-useful information is the fundamental objective of financial reporting. Information can be defined as decision-useful information if it assists the existing and potential capital providers (shareholders, lenders, bankers, and other creditors) in making their economic decisions. Zeff (2013) noted that decision-usefulness is considered the dominant role of contemporary financial reporting. Further, Badloe in 2011, identified the process of communicating both financial and non-financial information as useful information; as financial reporting, which is valued in making investment, credit, and

other business decisions. Accordingly, the second hypothesis of the research is developed as;

H2: The relevance of financial information disclosed in annual reports has a significant influence on investors’ decision-usefulness.

Based on the research objectives and hypothesis development, the conceptual framework is outlined as follows;

The present study adopts a user-oriented measurement approach, recognising investors as the most appropriate evaluators of decision usefulness. Here, In the present study, a quantitative research method is adopted due to its suitability for examining structured relationships among variables and for empirically testing hypotheses derived from established theoretical frameworks. Further, in this study, primary data were selected as the main data source due to the study’s focus on empirically examining the relationship between the “Relevance” and the decision-usefulness of investors.

According to the Colombo Stock Exchange Annual Report (2024), the CDS comprised 717,946 local account holders and 11,082 foreign account holders by the end of the reporting period. While these figures indicate a broad investor base, CDS registration alone does not necessarily reflect active market participation. Prior literature highlights that not all registered investors engage regularly in trading or financial analysis, and many accounts remain dormant over extended periods (De Vaus, 2014; Saunders et al., 2019). Moreover, the CSE does not publicly disclose information relating to the number of active investors or their trading frequency. As such, the total CDS population cannot be treated as the effective population for the purposes of this study.

In addition, the present research deliberately narrows its focus to investors who possess a certain level of accounting knowledge, educational exposure, or professional familiarity with financial reporting. This restriction is essential given that the study is evaluating the variable “Relevance” and its dimensions are capable of interpreting financial statements and related disclosures in a meaningful manner (IASB, 2018; Beest et al., 2009). Investors lacking sufficient accounting literacy may be unable to provide informed assessments, thereby introducing measurement error and reducing the reliability of the findings. Therefore, the unit of analysis is an

active investor in the Colombo Stock Exchange (CSE) who possesses an accounting background, knowledge, or understanding.

The sampling design adopted in this study employs a purposive selection of active CSE investors with accounting knowledge or background. The sampling frame is defined in a pragmatic and context-appropriate manner as investors who are currently engaged in CSE-related investment activities and who can be accessed through identifiable and relevant channels. These channels include stock brokerage firms, investment advisory services, professional accounting and finance networks, investor associations, postgraduate and professional accounting programmes, and CSE-focused investor forums. The present study employs a non-probability purposive sampling technique to select respondents who are most suitable for addressing the research objectives

Data were collected through a questionnaire survey of 397 Sri Lankan investors with accounting knowledge. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) was used to construct the model, supported by Exploratory and Confirmatory Factor Analyses for validation. Reliability and validity were assessed using indicator reliability, Average Variance Extracted (AVE), Cronbach’s alpha, and composite reliability.

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) is a statistical technique that is used to reduce data to a smaller set of summary variables and to explore the underlying theoretical structure of the phenomena. It is used to identify the structure of the relationship between the variable and the respondent.

According to the first iteration, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure (KMO value) is 0.939. In the rotated component matrix, 07 (Seven) factors/components were recorded. However, some cross-loading situations were reported in items: RFL04, RFL09, RFL10, RCF06, RFV05, and RCS04. Therefore, remove those items and re-run the factor analysis.

As per the results given in the second, the KMO value has been recorded as 0.931. Further, the number of factors is reduced to 06 (six). Simultaneously, RFL05 is identified with cross-loading. Therefore, removed this item and re-ran the factor analysis.

Finally, the KMO value is reported as 0.930, and accordingly, after running 03 (three) iterations, the variable “Relevance” was finalised with 28 information items and 06 (six) dimensions. The final result is given below in Table 03.

Table 03: Combination of information items of the variable ‘Relevance’

Information Dimension	Sub-information Item recognized in Conceptual Framework	Items deleted during the process of EFA	Items finalized through EFA
Forward-looking Information (RFL)	RFL01, RFL02, RFL03, RFL04, RFL05, RFL06, RFL07, RFL08, RFL09, RFL10.	RFL04, RFL05, RFL09, RFL10	RFL01, RFL02, RFL03, RFL06, RFL07, RFL08.
Cash Flow Information (RCF)	RCF01, RCF02, RCF03, RCF04, RCF05, RCF06	RCF06.	RCF01, RCF02, RCF03, RCF04, RCF05.
Segmental Information (RSI)	RSI01, RSI02, RSI03, RSI04, RSI05, RSI06.	-	RSI01, RSI02, RSI03, RSI04, RSI05, RSI06.
Information on Measuring Assets, Liabilities, and Equity at Fair Value (RFV)	RFV01, RFV02, RFV03, RFV04, RFV05.	RFV05	RFV01, RFV02, RFV03, RFV04.
Capital Structure Information (RCS)	RCS01, RCS02, RCS03, RCS04	RCS04	RCS01, RCS02, RCS03
Risk-Related Information (RRR)	RRR01, RRR02, RRR03, RRR04	-	RRR01, RRR02, RRR03, RRR04

B. Reliability Analysis

The reliability of a questionnaire is a way of assessing the quality of the measurement procedure used to collect data. Cronbach’s alpha determines the internal consistency or average correlation of items in a survey instrument to gauge the reliability of the questionnaire. Thus, Cronbach’s alpha is an index of reliability associated with the variation accounted for by the true score of the “underlying construct” (Santos, 1999). The alpha coefficient ranges in value from 0 to 1. Accordingly, the higher the score, the more reliable the generated scale is (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). The Cronbach’s Alpha values

of all the information dimensions are provided in Table 04 given below.

Table 04: Reliability analysis results table

Information Dimensions	Cronbach's Alpha
Forward-looking Information	0.920
Cash Flow Information	0.936
Segmental Information	0.916
Risk-related Information	0.868
Information on Fair Value	0.918
Capital Structure Information	0.875

C. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

CFA is used as a statistical technique which is applied to verify the factor structure of a set of observed variables. CFA allows the researcher to test the hypothesis that a relationship between observed variables and their underlying latent constructs exists. The researcher uses knowledge of the theory, empirical research, or both, postulates the relationship pattern a priori and then tests the hypothesis statistically. Based on these prior studies, it is decided that the factor loadings should be greater than 0.50 as proposed by Hair et al. (2007) for this research study. The factor loading of 28 information items relating to the variable “Relevance” is given below in Table 05.

Table 05: Factor Loadings results

Information Dimensions	Factor Loadings			
	Indicator	Loading	Indicator	Loading
Forward-looking Information (RFL)	RFL01	0.754	RFL06	0.884
	RFL02	0.692	RFL07	0.843
	RFL03	0.621	RFL08	0.763
Cash Flow Information (RCF)	RCF01	0.899	RCF04	0.898
	RCF02	0.856	RCF05	0.889
	RCF03	0.804		
Segmental Information (RSI)	RSI01	0.876	RSI04	0.785
	RSI02	0.808	RSI05	0.870
	RSI03	0.818	RSI06	0.661
Risk-Related Information (RRR)	RRR01	0.932	RRR03	0.812
	RRR02	0.877	RRR04	0.511
Information on Measuring Assets, Liabilities, and Equity at Fair Value (RFV)	RFV01	0.777	RFV03	0.886
	RFV02	0.868	RFV04	0.894
Capital Structure Information (RCS)	RCS01	0.888	RCS03	0.838
	RCS02	0.866		

sub-domains that are considered to measure the same construct (Hair Jr et. al., 2016; Hair, Black, Babin & Anderson, 2010). These scholars suggest that outer loadings of items and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) more appropriate for the evaluating convergent validity. Criteria for convergent validity, which require the AVE greater than 0.5, and standardized factor loading of all items not less than 0.5 (Hair Jr et. al., 2016). The outer loading values are also known as indicator reliability. High outer loadings on a construct show that the associated indicators associators have much in common, which is included in the construct. AVE defines as the mean value of the squared loadings of the indicators associated with the construct.

Internal consistency is used as the next criterion for assessing the measurement model. Internal consistency is typically a measure based on the correlations between different items on the same test (or the same subscale on a larger test). It measures whether several items that propose to measure the same general construct produce similar scores. This is assessed using Cronbach’s Alpha (CA) and Composite Reliability (CR). For the internal consistency to be considered acceptable, the coefficients of both CR and CA should be 0.70 or higher (Hair Jr et al., 2016).

The results of Table 6 presented below show the AVE, CR and CA results.

Table 06: Factor Loadings results

First-order construct	Convergent Validity (AVE)	Internal Validity	
		CR	CA
Forward-looking Information (RFL)	0.651	0.918	0.892
Cash Flow Information (RCF)	0.805	0.954	0.939
Segmental Information (RSI)	0.707	0.935	0.916
Risk-Related Information (RRR)	0.716	0.909	0.866
Information on Measuring Assets, Liabilities, and Equity at Fair Value (RFV)	0.800	0.941	0.916
Capital Structure Information (RCS)	0.831	0.898	0.937

E. Assessment of Collinearity, Indicator Contribution, and Significance

Before interpreting the structural and measurement model results, diagnostic assessments were conducted to ensure the

robustness of the estimates. Multicollinearity among indicators was examined using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). VIF values indicate the extent to which an indicator is linearly related to other indicators; values below the commonly accepted threshold (e.g., VIF < 5, or more conservatively < 3.3) suggest that multicollinearity is not a concern and that the indicators provide distinct information.

Outer weights were evaluated to assess the relative contribution of each indicator to its corresponding construct, particularly in the case of formative measurement models. Higher outer weight values indicate a stronger contribution of an indicator to the formation of the construct. Indicators with low outer weights may still be retained if they are theoretically important and/or exhibit significant outer loadings. Further, the statistical significance of outer weights was examined using bootstrapping procedures. The results reported in Table 7 summarise the VIF values, outer weights, and associated significance levels of the indicators.

Table 06: VIF values, outer weights, and associated significance levels.

Information Dimensions	Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)	Outer Weights	p-value	Significance (p < 0.05)
RFL	2.031	0.137	0.000	Yes
RCF	2.338	0.089	0.000	Yes
RSI	1.921	0.261	0.000	Yes
RRR	1.834	0.174	0.000	Yes
RFV	2.141	0.262	0.000	Yes
RCS	2.789	0.320	0.000	Yes

In this PLS path-model, statistics demonstrate that the 06 information dimensions, which can be measured by the 28 sub-information items (indicators), are suitable to represent the variable “Relevance”. Accordingly, with the results; H1 is accepted.

Development of Structural Models.

For the purpose of developing the FRQ measurement model, Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) in the SmartPLS software package has been used (Ringle et. al., 2015). As mentioned by Nasimento & Macedo (2016) and Lee et. al., (2011), PLS_SEM has been extensively used in the social sciences to analyze quantitative data. Accordingly, Struture model of this research has been developed as depicted in the figure 02.

Figure 02: Structural Model developed through SmartPLS

The path coefficient results obtained from the bootstrapping procedure in SmartPLS, as presented in Table 07, indicate that the construct **Relevance** makes a statistically significant contribution to its measurement.

Table 06: VIF values, outer weights, and associated significance levels.

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics	P Values
RCF -> R	0.265	0.278	0.036	7.467	0.000
RCS -> R	0.054	0.062	0.024	8.842	0.010
RFL -> R	0.143	0.145	0.056	2.568	0.011
RFV -> R	0.037	0.036	0.050	10.524	0.012
RRR -> R	0.023	0.013	0.024	9.311	0.000
RSI -> R	0.058	0.062	0.017	11.862	0.010

Table 06: R - Square results table

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Decision-Usefulness	0.769	0.767

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics	P Values
R > Decision-Usefulness	0.452	0.463	0.067	8.720	0.000

The R – square value in the table above is 0.769. It means the decision-usefulness of information provided through annual reports is influenced by “Relevance”. In other words, 76.9% change in decision-usefulness can be explained by the variable Revenue. Hair et al. (2011) & Hair et al. (2013) suggested in scholarly research that focuses on marketing issues, R2 values of 0.75, 0.50, or 0.25 for endogenous latent variables can, as a rough rule of thumb, be respectively described as substantial, moderate or weak. Accordingly, the R² value of 0.769 indicates the substantial influence of “Relevance” over the decisions made by the investors. Accordingly, H2 was also accepted.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study concentrates on achieving two research objectives: i. develop a measurement model to measure the “Relevance” of financial statements based on the literature, which facilitates the decision-making scenarios of Investors. and ii. explores the contribution of the developed measurement model of the variable “Relevance” toward providing decision-useful information for investors in the Sri Lankan context. Based on the qualitative characteristics mentioned in the Conceptual Framework issued by IASB, the dimensions of the variable “Relevance” have been developed, focusing on decision-usefulness. The VIF values, Outer weights, and significance values are used as an important measure of collinearity in the context of PLS-SEM.

In the development of the construct, 28 indicators under 06 information dimensions are employed based on the Hierarchical Component Model (HCM) approach. When achieving the first research objective, the coefficients of all the dimensions significantly contributed towards the measurement of “Relevance”. Accordingly, with the results, H1 is accepted.

Secondly; this research aims to explore the contribution of the “Relevance” toward providing decision-useful information for investors. The results recognized a substantial influence of relevance over the decisions made by the investors; hence, H2 is accepted. Scholars such as; Akeju & Babatunde (2017), Beest et al. (2009), Braam & Beest (2013), and Herath & Albarqi (2017) also prove the decision-usefulness of quality information provided through financial reports.

Finally, this study concluded that investors, as users of financial reports, can use relevant financial information presented in financial reports since the financial reports have been prepared based on the “Relevance” characteristics identified by the International Accounting Standard Board, and it gives useful information in making their investment decisions.

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